

FlowCam-Zooprocess user manual and procedures at the Quantitative Imaging Platform of Villefranche-sur-Mer (PIQv)

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1. Introduction

The FlowCam (Yokogawa Fluid Imaging Technologies Inc.) is an imaging system for the measurement and classification of organisms and particles present in a liquid. It is suitable for several sizes of planktonic organisms depending on the flow cell, objective and pump used. See also : <https://www.fluidimaging.com/>

The Villefranche-sur-Mer Quantitative Imaging Platform has worked on more than 150 projects with FlowCam since its creation. As a result of these years of experience, the PIQv has implemented analysis and quality control procedures. The aim of this manual is to present these rules and to highlight best practices for guaranteeing data quality and the use of Ecotaxa. The PIQv accepts no responsibility for any damage to the FlowCam resulting from misinterpretation of this manual.

The PIQv uses the FlowCam to analyse microplankton between 20 and 200 μm . This manual therefore presents the 300 μm flow cell, the x4 objective and the 5 mL pump but it is possible to use other flow cells, objectives and syringes to observe smaller or larger plankton:

Objective Lens	FOV Flow Cell (μm)	Syringe (mL)	Suggested Flow Rate (mL/min)	Minimum Particle Size (μm)	Maximum Particle Size (μm)	Autolmage Rate Range (frames/s)	Range Efficiency (%)
2X	1000	12.5	10	70*	1000	5 to 10	51.7 to 103.3
4X	600	5.0	0.9	5**	600	4 to 11	33.5 to 99.2
4X	300	5.0	0.9	5**	300	4 to 11	33.5 to 99.2
10X	100	1.0	0.15	2**	100	10 to 41	24.3 to 99.5
20X	50	0.5	0.03	0.9**	50	20 to 84	33.0 to 99.7

*EG 125–255, **EG 150–255

In addition, the PIQv is interested in all the particles in a sample, not just the living ones, which is why it only uses the Autolmage Mode. Consequently, the Trigger Mode is not presented in this manual. It also describes the steps for installing and preparing the FlowCam before and after analysis, which are also described in the Yokogawa Fluid Imaging Technologies manual, however the PIQv has chosen to give more details and warnings for these steps.

This working protocol might be adjusted by users according to their experience and needs in order to take advantage of the tools provided by the application. We recommend always keeping the default settings offered by Zooprocess.

The typical analysis sequence is as follow:

- 1) Context configuration
- 2) Preview before acquisition
- 3) Acquisition Autolmage Mode
- 4) Export context file
- 5) Fill in sample metadata

- 6) Process PID, TSV and Vignettes
- 7) Import in EcoTaxa to predict identification and manually validate or correct the prediction made by the application.

2. Powering on the analyzer

- To power on, switch on the button behind the FlowCam.

- Then press the round power button on the top right of the analyzer to initialise its internal pump and the computer.

- The power button turns blue and you should see the startup process begin on the monitor.

3. Project creation with Zooprocess

- Launch ImageJ/Zooprocess and choose “Create NEW project” in ImageJ/Zooprocess then click on “OK” button.

- Enter the serial number of your FlowCam.

The serial number is available inside your FlowCam.

- ① Select the drive in which you want your project to be created. ② You can decide if you want to add the serial number of your FlowCam at the start of the project name (in this case the list of projects will be sorted by serial number of FlowCam if you have more than one) or at the end (in this case the list of projects will be sorted by alphabetical order). ③ Choose the name of your project (do not add the "flowcam_" prefix ; Zooprocess will automatically add it). **AVOID using special characters in the name of your project.**

PROJECT MANAGER version 8.20

NEW project

Flowcam sn : 10787

Select drive (Do not select CD drive)!

① Z:\

Enter project name (do not include the instrument s/n in the project name)

Choose the position of the Zooscan serial number to be added to the project name

② end

③ projectname

OK Cancel

- Choose “Raw images (recommended)” and click on the “OK” button. This choice will enable Zooprocess to work on your raw images and therefore to subtract the background, segment your images and calculate all the associated morphometric measurements. The ecotaxa.tsv table will be created for import into EcoTaxa.

- Keep the default settings. There are very few fields that you may have to change. These fields are in **bold**. The ESD limits and the Maximum numbers of images and objects which depend on the FlowCam application settings have to be checked carefully. Click on the “OK” button when you are OK with the settings.

- Method to subtract background: should be set as displayed on the image above.
 - **Threshold for segmentation**: will be used to extract objects from the background of images (**245 for Benchtop FlowCam (B&W images) and 240 for FlowCam V8000 (color images)**).
 - **Gamma for vignette display**: 0.5 – 5. Utilised to enhance the visual aspect of vignettes. It has no effect on measurements; applies only on B&W images
 - **Length of scale line (μm)**: length of the scale bar in vignettes. It utilizes the Pixel size..
 - **ESD min (μm)**: minimum size of objects to be analyzed.
 - **ESD max (μm)**: can help remove too big targets.
 - **Maximum number of IMAGES to be analyzed**: stop criteria.
 - **Maximum number of OBJECTS to be analyzed**: stop criteria.
 - Remove objects touching sides: helps remove truncated objects.
 - Remove duplicates: helps remove duplicates (objects sucked in the cell).
 - Grey level auto adjust: helps compensate for variations of image intensity over time for one sample.
- When your project is created, you get this message

A project is a folder where images and data of a cruise, survey or experiment will be saved. A project thus contains many samples and acquisitions. The project will be created on the selected drive and all files from this project will later be saved in the specific subfolders.

4. Sample preparation

- 1 Place a funnel in the fixative bin.
- 2 Place a 20 µm sieve in the funnel.
- 3 Empty the sample into the sieve.
- 4 Use fresh water or filtered sea water bottles and squeeze bottles to:
 - rinse the jar and make sure there is nothing left.
 - rinse the sieve with water to remove as much fixative as possible.

- 1 In the sink, place a funnel in a new 20 or 50 µm sieve depending on the mesh size.
- 2 Place a 200 µm sieve in the funnel.
- 3 Empty the first 20 µm sieve containing the sample into the 200 µm sieve, rinsing with water.
- 4 Pass a fine stream of fresh water or filtered sea water over the 200 µm sieve to drop organisms <200 µm into the 20 or 50 µm sieve below.
- 5 Keep your fraction >200 µm in a basin of water.

- 1 Empty the 20 or 50 µm sieve into a graduated burette using fresh water or filtered sea water bottles and squeeze bottles.
- 2 Top up with fresh water or filtered sea water to reach a suitable concentration for the FlowCam. Preferably, reach a round number.

5. FlowCam preparation

5.1 Installing the Flow Cell

Note 1: When changing the flow cell, you must also change the objective lens and the pump syringe.

Objective Lens	FOV Flow Cell (μm)	Syringe (mL)
2X	1000	12.5
4X	600	5.0
4X	300	5.0
10X	100	1.0
20X	50	0.5

- Unscrew the two red screws: do not remove them completely. The two screws **must not** stick out the inside to avoid damaging the cell (very fragile and expensive) during its installation.
Remove the black retainer.

- There are two tubes : one upper tubing + one lower tubing (direction does not matter).

- Put the upper tubing in the sample input port then screw it. **DO NOT FORCE** : plastic pieces are fragile
 - o 1 Place the tube and insert it up to the end
 - o 2 Insert it in the black holder (to place it straight and help to screw straight)
 - o 3 Screw
 - o 4 Remove to the black holder (to not force on the flow cell in any case)

- Put the lower tubing in the syringe pump manifold then screw it.

- Remove the flow cell from its protective case and inspect it for any damage
 - The flow cell is fragile. Handle it carefully to ensure you do not damage it.**
 - Do not touch the faces of the flow cell with your fingers. If necessary, clean it with Kimtech paper and fresh water.**

- Put the lower tubing to the bottom of the flow cell. The engraved serial number and the red mark indicate the top. Then screw it **by handling the bottom of the flow cell**

Etched serial number and the red mark

Handle the bottom of the flow cell

Screwed lower tubing to the flow cell **by handling the bottom of the flow cell**

- Put the upper tubing to the top of the flow cell. Then screw it **by handling the top of the flow cell.**

Handle the top of the flow cell

Screwed upper tubing to the flow cell **by handling the top of the flow cell**

- Place **gently** the upper tubing in the fluid position slot.

Fluid position slot

- **With your two fingers at the top and the bottom of the flow cell**, place it **gently** into its associated opening. The red mark must be in front of you.

- Place the flow cell retainer into the slot so that the flow cell is held in place. If there is resistance: gently shift the cell to the left.

- Screw the two red screws.

5.2 Installing the Objective Lens

Note: When changing the objective lens to another, you must also change the flow cell and the pump syringe.

Objective Lens	FOV Flow Cell (μm)	Syringe (mL)
2X	1000	12.5
4X	600	5.0
4X	300	5.0
10X	100	1.0
20X	50	0.5

- Open the objective lens shroud by pulling the silver knob.

- Launch VisualSpreadsheet program, select Setup -> Objective -> Install.

- This causes the stage that holds the objective lens to move to the left so you can access the objective lens fitting.

BE CAREFUL ! Check the distance : the stage that holds the objective lens MUST BE to the left before continuing the installation.

OK

NOT OK

- You have a message “Install Objective” from VisualSpreadsheet program. Do **not** click yet.

- Remove the objective lens from its protective case.

- If there is already an objective lens, remove it from its container by unscrewing. Gently thread the new lens clockwise into the fitting. Do **not** overtighten.

- Now click on the 2 “OK” buttons. The stage moves the objective lens stage back into position and the VisualSpreadsheet status bar displays the new objective lens value. You can close the objective compartment.

5.3 Installing the Pump Syringe

Note: When changing the pump syringe to another, you must also change the flow cell and the objective lens.

Objective Lens	FOV Flow Cell (µm)	Syringe (mL)
2X	1000	12.5
4X	600	5.0
4X	300	5.0
10X	100	1.0
20X	50	0.5

- Launch VisualSpreadsheet program, select Setup -> Fluidics. The Pump Controller dialog opens. Click on “Change” button under the Syringe options.

- A message asks if you want to change the syringe. Click on “Yes”

- Turn the plunger lock screw counterclockwise as far as it will go without it falling out. Then click on “OK” button. The plunger base moves down to allow for removal.

- If there is already a syringe, unscrew it from the pump manifold, and remove it. Click on “OK” button.

- **Make sure that the plunger is perfectly centred in the syringe.**

- Screw the new syringe into the pump manifold, and centre the plunger in the syringe. Click on the “OK” button. The plunger base moves back into place.

- Securely tighten the plunger lock screw by turning it clockwise. Click on “OK” button.

- The “Select Syringe Size” dialog appears. Select the applicable size from the Syringe Size dropdown list and click on “OK” button.

- Clean the previous syringe and replace it in its container.

6. Autofocus

Note1:

Before starting, make sure that the automatic clean and rinse is deactivated so that you can choose to start it whenever you want, as it is a time-consuming operation.

Note2:

You only need to perform the autofocus routine upon initial startup, and after you change the flow cell or the objective lens.

- Launch VisualSpreadsheet program, click on "Camera View" button.

- The acceptable region lies within the red indicator lines. These red lines have to be centred within the grey lines, which represent the walls of the flow cell. Align the red indicator lines as close as possible within the flow cell using the positioning knob located to the left of the flow cell assembly in the interior of the analyzer.

However, since zooprocess version 8.22, this region is automatically recalculated and corrected during the process when the RAW images are recorded

- Put the pipette tip and fill in with approximately 2-3 mL of deionized water or Milli-Q® water.

- Homogenise the bead solution by shaking it and put 5 drops in deionized water or Milli-Q® water of pipette tip.

- Click on “Pump Control” and “Start Pump” buttons.

- When the beads appear in the flow cell, click on “Pause Pump” button.

- Click on the “Autofocus” button and follow the onscreen prompts.

- Select Best Focus Image: the algorithm depending upon whether you are running uniform materials for primarily counting, or varied particles for image quality. The stage assembly orients itself depending upon the selection after the routine is completed.

- The pump draws the sample into the flow cell and the autofocus starts.

- When the autofocus is finished, the message “Auto Focus Completed” appears. To empty your flow cell, click on “Start Flush Flow Cell” button, fill in your pipette tip with deionized water or Milli-Q® water to clean your flow cell then click on “Stop Flush Flow Cell” when it is finished.

Deionized water or Milli-Q® water in pipette tip

- Close “Setup and Focus Mode” windows.

7. Context Configuration: AutoImage Mode

The Context dialog contains the settings used by the FlowCam particle analyzer to capture particles of interest during a sample analysis. The settings will be saved in a context file (*filename.ctx*) within the raw folder of your project.

You define a context file per project.

Objective Lens	FOV Flow Cell (µm)	Syringe (mL)	Suggested Flow Rate (mL/min)	Minimum Particle Size (µm)	Maximum Particle Size (µm)	AutoImage Rate Range (frames/s)	Range Efficiency (%)
2X	1000	12.5	10	70*	1000	5 to 10	51.7 to 103.3
4X	600	5.0	0.9	5**	600	4 to 11	33.5 to 99.2
4X	300	5.0	0.9	5**	300	4 to 11	33.5 to 99.2
10X	100	1.0	0.15	2**	100	10 to 41	24.3 to 99.5
20X	50	0.5	0.03	0.9**	50	20 to 84	33.0 to 99.7

*EG 125–255, **EG 150–255

- Launch VisualSpreadsheet program and click on “Context” button.

Capture Tab

Particle Capture:

Distance in µm between 2 objects to consider them as Different = 20 µm + Close Holes = 2

Particles defined by:

Definition of the threshold of the segmentation from VisualSpreadsheet to retain a particle.

Images:

Setting of the image border : 3 pixels.

Save Raw Camera Images within raw folder.

Max Raw Images a low limit will stop the acquisition before the end (even if the stop conditions have been met), fill in 99999 by default.

Acceptable Region:

Definition of the area that will be captured on the cell by the camera: **do not change these values.**

Fluidics Tab

Settings: Pump characteristics

Enter a large sample volume, for example 100 mL. The stop conditions are defined by the analysis time or number of images, and not by the sample volume.

At each acquisition, try to achieve a large value of efficiency by changing Flow rate and Autolmage Rate.

BUT the value must NOT BE too high otherwise there is a warning:

Stop Tab

Stop conditions: Analysis characteristics

The camera will stop the acquisition according to these characteristics.

Here, if at 45 minutes of acquisition the number of 10 000 particles has not been reached, the camera will stop the acquisition and the pump will stop.

Recalibration: schedule regular recalibration, for example every 2 minutes. This allows the VisualSpreadsheet to recalibrate to the background and not get stuck on a particle held in the flow cell during acquisition.

Report Tab

In Exports, check Export list summary when run terminates.

The classification is done using the EcoTaxa web application.

Flow Cell Tab

Information on the flow cell and tubing

Capture Filter Tab

Basic Size Acquisition Filter: Images characteristics

Choose the good ESD min according the mesh size of your net

Note Tab: to put some notes and

Run Summary Tab: summary at the end of acquisition

- Once the configurations are defined, save them as **“autoimagemode_current_context_projectname”** in the Load tab.

8. Load context file and define the path of your analyses

You will then only have to load this “autoimagemode_current_context_projectname” and define the path of your analyses for the next starts of the acquisition.

- To load your context file:

- To define the path of your analyses:

Your analyses have to be registered in the raw folder of your project:

- back
- config
- docs
- meta
- PID_process
- raw**
- results
- work

9. Preview before Image Acquisition: AutoImage No Save

Before starting,

- **Make sure that the automatic clean and rinse is deactivated so that you can choose to start it whenever you want, as it is a time-consuming operation.**

= Uncheck then close the Fluidics window

- **Make sure that your waste is empty.**
- **Define the path of your analyses**
- **Load your context file + In Fluidics Tab, you must choose the Flow rate and AutoImage Rate. If you do not have much plankton, you can put a higher Flow rate (for example, 3-4 mL/min) but in this case, you have to also put a higher AutoImage Rate until you reach a large Efficiency:**

The good value for Efficiency must be around 70%

BUT the value NOT BE too high otherwise there is a warning:

To launch the preview step :

- Fill in the pipette tip with sample and
- Click on camera view and pump until removing air bubbles (**air bubbles in the flow cell stop of the acquisition**)
- Click on “Analyse” -> “AutoImage Mode (No Save)”

Manual Focus, if needed

- Check that your images are in focus and that they are well captured by the camera: you can increase or decrease the Flow rate and the Autolmage Rate (watch out for the efficiency) in your Context (Fluidics tab : see [Chapter 7](#)).
- Eventually fine tune the focus using the manual focus option

10.Acquisition: AutoImage Mode with VisualSpreadsheet

Before starting

- Make sure that the automatic clean and rinse is deactivated so that you can choose to start it whenever you want, as it is a time-consuming operation.

= Uncheck
then close the
Fluidics
window

- Make sure that your waste is empty.
- Define the path of your analyses
- Load your context file + In Fluidics Tab, you must choose the Flow rate and AutoImage Rate. If your sample concentration is low, you can set a high flow rate (for example, 3-4 mL/min) but in this case, you have to also set a high AutoImage Rate until you reach a sufficient Efficiency:

The good value for Efficiency must be around 70%

BUT the value NOT BE too high otherwise there is a warning:

- After Autolmage No Save, click on “Analyse” -> “Autolmage Mode” or directly on Autolmage Mode button and fill in the Stop Conditions: for example, 10 000 particles + 45 minutes.

OR

The analysis will stop automatically when the number of imaged objects reaches the defined value (10000) or when the analysis reaches the time delay (45 minutes) in case of a low plankton concentration.

You must carefully consider the naming convention of your samples before their analysis with the FlowCam as it is not possible to change the name of your samples afterward.

1. **WARNING:** your file name have to be called: flowcam_ samplename.lst to be recognized by Zooprocess
2. In your file name, do not use spaces (use underscore “_”), capital letters, accents or special characters
3. The analysis starts when you click on the “OK” button

- Homogenise the sample regularly in the funnel using the pipetman.
- Do not hesitate to use “Tools” → “Recalibrate” if objects get attached to the glass or get unstuck
- Do not hesitate to pinch the tube between the flow cell and the pump to unstuck objects (ideally should be done every 2-3 minutes to be sure that no plankton clogs are created).

Big bubbles stops the acquisition (before been imaged), make sure to avoid creating large bubbles

When the acquisition finishes, the AutoImage Mode windows closes, you **MUST** then export the context file “**autoimagemode_current_context_projectname**” in your analysis folder “flowcam_sampleID”:

“File” ☞ “Context...” ☞ check “autoimagemode_current_context_projectname” ☞ choose the export directory by clicking on “...” ☞ choose your sample acquisition folder in raw folder ☞ then click on “Export” button

Close windows.

Check in your sample acquisition folder if the context is inside:

Perform an initial quality control of the acquisition, checking that objects have been imaged evenly along the flow cell:

11.Recover the sample

- Recover all the sample from the pipette tip using the pipetman.
- Fill the funnel with fresh water (sea water if you have) and run the pump for 2 cycles to get back any organisms remaining in the circuit: Setup -> Fluidics -> Flush.

When the 2 cycles are complete,

- ① empty the waste bottle into the burette containing the initial sample
- ② use fresh water or filtered sea water squeeze bottle to get back all organisms into the burette

- ① empty the burette into a 20 or 50 μm sieve depending on the mesh size of the net used for sampling
- ② use fresh water or filtered sea water squeeze bottle to get back all organisms

If you want to preserve the sample, empty the 20 or 50 μm sieve into a jar and fill with your fixative using an extraction hood if imposed by the type of fixative.

12. Clean and Rinse

- Fill in the rinse bottle with deionized water or Milli-Q® water.
Fill in the cleaner bottle with deionized water or Milli-Q® water + 3-5% of cleaner Citrajel.

- Launch VisualSpreadsheet program, select Setup -> Fluidics, choose the number of cycles to perform for clean and for rinse (at least 2 cycles). Check the 2 boxes then click on the “Clean/Rinse” button.

- Be patient during the clean and rinse.

13. Uninstall the FlowCam

Warning: In this chapter, we describe how to uninstall the flow cell, the objective lens and the pump syringe, but please note that the PIQv never uninstalls the FlowCam between each analysis. The PIQv is only uninstalled for cleaning the tools once a month. Uninstalling the FlowCam presents a risk for the cell in particular, which is very fragile because it is made of glass and its support is made of steel.

13.1 Uninstalling the Flow Cell

- Unscrew the two red screws: do not remove them completely. The two screws **must not** stick out the inside to avoid damaging the cell when it is uninstalled. Remove the black retainer.

- In handling the Flow Cell, unscrew the upper tubing and lower tubing.

- Put back the black retainer and gently tighten the two red screws.

Unscrew the upper tubing **by handling the top of the flow cell** and unscrew the lower tubing **by handling the bottom of the flow cell**.

Unscrew upper tubing **by handling the top of the flow cell**

Screwed lower tubing to the flow cell **by handling the bottom of the flow cell**

- **The flow cell is fragile. Handle it carefully to ensure you do not damage it.**
- **Do not touch the faces of the flow cell with your fingers. If necessary, clean it with Kimtech paper and fresh water.**

- Place back the flow cell in its protective case and the upper + lower tubings in a ziplock bag. Put them back in the FlowCam case (see packing list):

13.2 Uninstalling the Objective Lens

- Launch VisualSpreadsheet program, select Setup ▾ Objective ▾ Remove.

- This causes the stage that holds the objective lens to move to the left so you can access the objective lens fitting.

- Unscrew the objective lens and replace it in its protective case and in the FlowCam case.

- Click on the “OK” button.

13.3 Uninstalling the Pump Syringe

- Launch VisualSpreadsheet program, select Setup -> Fluidics. The Pump Controller dialog opens. Click on “Change” button under the Syringe options.

- A message asks if you want to change the syringe. Click on “Yes” button.

- Turn the plunger lock screw counterclockwise **as far as it will go without it falling out.** Then click on “OK” button. The plunger base moves down to allow for removal.

- Unscrew the syringe from the pump manifold, and remove it. Click on “OK” button.

- Replace the syringe in its protective case and in the FlowCam case.

- Turn the plunger lock screw clockwise then click on “OK” twice.

plunger
lock screw

- The “Select Syringe Size” dialog appears. Select the applicable size from the Syringe Size dropdown list and click on the “OK” button.

14. Maintenance after analyse

- Make sure that there is no more liquid in the system.
- You can remove the pipette tip and sampling funnel and undo the rest of the circuit (objective, Flow Cell and syringe) in no particular order (see [Chapter 5](#)).
- Flow Cell
 - To extend the longevity of the flow cells, always handle them with care.
 - If you suspect that the flow cell is obstructed, remove the flow cell from the upper and lower tubing connections, and clean it as follows:
 - Use a warm water jet first, followed by dilute detergent, and then a warm water jet to rinse.
 - Do not use an ultrasonic cleaner.
 - Do not blow dry flow cells with compressed air.
 - Never use tap water with flow cells.
 - Use a final rinse of deionized water.
- Never run corrosive materials, such as bleach or acids, through the flow cells.
- Never leave a flow cell with a sample or some material inside when not using the analyzer.
- Inspect the flow cell channel frequently for contamination or obstructions. The inspection should include removing the tubing from each end to look into the channel.
- Carefully inspect your flow cell using a compound microscope or magnifying lens, especially the ends of the flow cell chamber.
- Clean the outside of the cell by wiping well with a Kimtech paper.
- Regular cleaning of your FOV flow cell is recommended. Use the following instructions to unclog and clean your FOV flow cell. Wear gloves when handling the flow cell.

1. If the flow cell is clogged, locate the clog using a microscope or magnifying glass.
2. Assemble the syringe and luer-lock coupler (provided in the FOV flow cell cleaning kit).
3. Draw ~2 mL of detergent solution into the syringe and attach it to the end of the flow cell opposite the clog.
4. Push or pull the detergent through the flow cell.

5. Repeat the flush with deionized water.
6. Inspect the flow cell again to confirm that the clog has been removed.
7. Clean the exterior of the flow cell with low-lint lens paper prior to reinstallation.
8. For stubborn clogs, the FOV flow cell can be soaked in warm water or detergent prior to performing the syringe purge.

15. Report of metadata to the laboratory notebook

Fill in these columns in your laboratory notebook:

Sample ID	Start Time	End Time	Burette Volume mL	Sample Volume Aspirated mL	Particles per Image	Comments
-----------	------------	----------	-------------------	----------------------------	---------------------	----------

To Report on the lab notebook Start Time, End Time, Sample Volume Aspirated and Particles per Image:

- Go to your project.
- Open the raw directory.
- Open the directory of your sample Flowcam_XXXXXXXXXX..
- Open the file Flowcam_XXXXXXXXXX_summary.csv.

Name	Date modified	Type
cal_image_000001.tif	3/2/2022 5:04 PM	TIF File
flowcam_sampleID_summary.csv	3/2/2022 5:10 PM	Microsoft Excel C...
rawfile_000000.tif	3/2/2022 5:04 PM	TIF File
rawfile_000001.tif	3/2/2022 5:04 PM	TIF File
rawfile_000002.tif	3/2/2022 5:04 PM	TIF File
rawfile_000003.tif	3/2/2022 5:04 PM	TIF File
rawfile_000004.tif	3/2/2022 5:04 PM	TIF File
rawfile_000005.tif	3/2/2022 5:04 PM	TIF File

	A	B
1	=====Run Summaries=====	
2		
3	Name: flowcam_sampleID	
4		
5	Run:	
6	Mode	AutoImage
7	Priming Method	manual prime with sample
8	Flow Rate	1.000 ml/min
9	Recalibrations	0
10	Stop Reason	Particle Count
11	Sample Volume Aspirated	6.3287 ml
12	Sample Volume Processed	6.1471 ml
13	Fluid Volume Imaged	1.1550 ml
14	Efficiency	18.79%
15	Particle Count	1500
16		
17	Images:	
18	Total	1079
19	Used	802
20	Percentage Used	74.33%
21	Particles Per Image	1.39
22	Frame Rate	2.93 fps
23	Background Intensity Mean	150.11
24	Background Intensity Min	148.78
25	Background Intensity Max	151.01
26		
27	Date/Time:	
28	Start Time	2022-03-02 17:03:34
29	End Time	2022-03-02 17:10:12
30	Sampling Time	00:06:08
31		
32	Environment	VisualSpreadsheet5 5.6.14
33	Software	VisualSpreadsheet5 5.6.14

16.Fill in sample metadata with Zooprocess

Zooprocess offers to fill the metadata of the samples after they have been imaged using the FlowCam. These metadata are necessary for the later reconstruction of the plankton concentrations and should be carefully documented.

Open ImageJ/Zooprocess, choose your project, choose “Fill in the sample or profile metadata” tool then follow the procedure.

Everytime you start filling the metadata of a sample, the metadata of the previous sample are displayed in the fields in the form. Do not forget to check them and change if necessary:

The diagram illustrates the workflow for filling sample metadata in Zooprocess. It starts with the ImageJ logo, followed by the Zooprocess main window where a project is selected. A dropdown menu is used to choose the 'Fill in the sample or profile metadata' tool. This leads to the 'FLOWCAM METADATA' dialog, where a sample is selected. Finally, the 'METADATA' dialog is shown with fields for Project, SampleID, and RAW filename.

ZOOPROCESS version 8.23 (2023/11/21)

Instrument : FLOWCAM
ZOOPROCESS
for ImageJ version 1.41o

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Please refer to Zooprocess and ImageJ if used for Publication
<http://rsb.info.nih.gov/ij/index.html>

SELECT (or CREATE) PROJECT
Z:\flowcam_projectname_sn10787

OK Cancel

SELECT TOOL for FLOWCAM

- Fill in the sample or profile metadata
- Fill in the sample or profile metadata
- Process PID, TSV and VIGNETTES
- Edit the sample or profile metadata

OK Cancel

SWITCH to ADVANCED mode

FLOWCAM METADATA version : 8.20

Project : Z:\flowcam_projectname_sn10787
Metadatafile = Flowcam_header_projectname_sn10787.txt

SELECT Sample to add or press CANCEL to end
flowcam_sample_ID

OK Cancel

METADATA version = 8.20

Project : projectname_sn10787

ENTER SampleID, (no extension or space character allowed)

RAW filename : sample_ID
sample_ID

OK Cancel

WINDOW #1 POSITIONS (version: 8.17)

SAMPLE ID : phyto20230131_sn476 (phyto20230131_sn476)
 Project : ptb_phyto_2023_pelagos_sn476

Cruise or scientific program: xx
 Sampling operator (first and last names): jea
 Flowcam operator (first and last names): gab
 Station Id (must start with alphanumeric char, "nan" if unknown): xx

Bottom depth (m): 999
 Sampling date (YYYYMMDD-HHMM): 20230131-1830
 LATITUDE (degree): 43
 LATITUDE (minute): 41
 LATITUDE (NS): N
 STARTING LONGITUDE (degree): 7
 STARTING LONGITUDE (minute): 18
 STARTING LONGITUDE (EW): E

Sampling gear: Net
 Sampling duration (minute) 99999 if not documented: 999
 Maximum Depth, 99999 if unknown (m) : Zmax: 75
 Minimum Depth, 99999 if unknown (m) : Zmin: 0
 Depth Quality Flag:
 Ship: sagitta
 Ship speed (knots) 99999 if not documented: 99999
 CTD reference (filename): nan
 OTHER reference (filename): PHP023031F

ENDING LATITUDE (degree): 0
 ENDING LATITUDE (minute): 0
 ENDING LATITUDE (NS): N
 ENDING LONGITUDE (degree): 0
 ENDING LONGITUDE (minute): 0
 ENDING LONGITUDE (EW): E

WINDOW #2 NETS (version: 8.17)

SAMPLE ID : phyto20230131_sn476 (phyto20230131_sn476)
 Project : ptb_phyto_2023_pelagos_sn476

Tow type:
 Net type (WP2, JB, Regent, Omori, Multinet...): nan
 Net mesh (µm): 99999
 Net opening surface (m2): 99999
 Cable speed (m/s) 99999 if not documented: 99999
 Cable angle from vertical (°) 99999 if not documented: 99999
 Cable length (m) 99999 if not documented: 99999
 Flowmeter START: 99999
 Flowmeter END: 99999
 Flowmeter TYPE: nan

WINDOW #3 SAMPLE (version: 8.17)

SAMPLE ID : phyto20230131_sn476 (phyto20230131_sn476)
 Project : ptb_phyto_2023_pelagos_sn476

if net sampling : number of tow in the same sample: 1
 Initial collected volume (m3), (sum of the nets), 999999 if unknown: 1
 Quality Flag of the Initial collected volume:
 Concentrated or Diluted water volume (from initial) (ml): 1400
 Dilution method: nan
 Fixative: nan
 Sieve MIN mesh size (99999 if unknown) (µm): 99999
 Sieve MAX mesh size (99999 if unknown) (µm): 99999
 Add sample comment: 15825000
 BARCODE: nan
 Nb of jars for the sample, 99999 if not documented: 99999
 JAR airiness:
 SAMPLE richness:
 SAMPLE conditioning:
 SAMPLE content:

FLOWCAM METADATA version : 8.20

Project : Z:\flowcam_projectname_sn10787

Metadatafile = Flowcam_header_projectname_sn10787.txt

SELECT Sample to add or press CANCEL to end

flowcam_sample_ID - (done) ▾

OK Cancel

Files created by Zooprocess after the filling operation:

The table “Flowcam_header_projectname.txt” lists all the samples and associated metadata you have documented and a “meta.txt” is created containing the sample metadata into each sample subfolder of the work folder.

N.B.: You can modify the metadata (except the sample name) at any time between all the processing steps clicking “Edit sample/profile metadata” in the options list.

The tool corrects the metadata in the tables of the meta folder and inside all files related to the sample anywhere in the project.

17. How to export the context file ?

The context file is essential for launching the process PID, TSV and image (see [Chapter 18](#)).

- Launch VisualSpreadsheet program, select “File” → “Open Data”
- Click on “Open Data” button into the window “Select Data”

- ① Select “Runs” → ② Select the analysis for which you wish to export the context file → ③ Click on “Open” button

- ① Select your analysis → ② Click on “OK” button

- Your analysis opens → click on "File" → "Export" → "Context" and in the new window export ① the correct context ② by choosing the path and ③ by clicking on “Export” button

18. Quality control and Process PID, TSV and Vignettes with Zooprocess

To create the images and ecotaxa_*.tsv for import into EcoTaxa, you must launch the “Process PID, TSV and VIGNETTES” tool in Zooprocess. The ecotaxa_*.tsv file contains all data and all useful metadata from the PID file. This table and images will be both imported into the EcoTaxa application (<http://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/>) to predict and classify the organisms.

- Open ImageJ/Zooprocess, select your project and choose “Process PID, TSV and VIGNETTES” tool.

- ① Let check “Use the new process (RGB images only) ?” to process with the last version of Zooprocess.
- ② This part allows Zooprocess to automatically recalculate and correct the acceptable region (see Chapter 6). We strongly recommend using this first option.

- **To use the new RGB image process, your threshold for segmentation (“upper”) must be 245.** If you did not change this parameter when you created your project (see [Chapter 3](#)), you can change now by clicking on the “Yes” button.

- **Before the process, Zooprocess asks you if you want it to check all your acquisitions and detect any problems. We strongly recommend this step.**

- At the end of this step, this message summarises the check

In your project, you also get a log file containing a more complete summary.

All samples must be “OK for processing” before the process. Correct the problems (files) and redo the tests if necessary till all samples can be processed.

```
Log_files_to_process_20240514_0914.txt - Bloc-notes
Fichier Edition Format Affichage Aide
----- START -----
1 samples in the Z:\flowcam_projectname_sn10787\meta\Flowcam_header_projectname_sn10787.txt file.
1 raw folders in Z:\flowcam_projectname_sn10787\raw\ are being checked.
-----1 / 1-----
Filename= sample_ID
SampleId= sample_id
CTX file OK : autoimagemode_current_context_projectname.ctx
summary.csv may contain '' or tabs, process possible !
Summary file OK : summary.csv
=> sample_id OK for processing

-----
WARNINGS on the samples to process :
-----

sample_id: summary.csv may contain '' or tabs, process possible !
----- END -----
```

- At the end of process, you have to read this message:

Files created during the process from Zooprocess in work folder

Border_control_image: acceptable region defined by you in Visual Spreadsheet

Border_control_image_corrected: acceptable region corrected and used by Zooprocess

ecotaxa_... .tsv: contains all data and all useful metadata issued from the .pid file

FlowCam_... .txt: measurements table of each objects

Log.txt: tracking file

images.jpg: vignettes issued from the rawfiles_XXXXXX.tif

_dat1.pid: issued from several files (meta, settings, measurements)

meta.txt: all metadata issued from meta folder

Border_control_image:
Acceptable region before correction

Border_control_image_corrected:
Acceptable region after correction

19. Tag duplicate

When samples are acquired, foreign materials like dirt, debris, clumps of particles, or even living organisms can stick to the flow cell surface. As the flow continues, these materials are repeatedly captured in images, leading to the appearance of duplicate objects after segmentation.

To address this, Zooprocess identifies these duplicate images during the tsv and image processing stages. It then marks them with a '2' in the ecotaxa.tsv table. **This tag is done automatically in Zooprocess version 8.31.**

If your projects were processed with software versions older than 8.31, you can now utilize the tagging option independently, following a software update to 8.31 or a newer version.

Open ImageJ/Zooprocess, select your project and switch to advanced mode. Choose the "Tag..." tool.

At the end, you have to have “Normal end...” message.

You duplicate are now marked with a '2' in the ecotaxa.tsv table, making it easier to filter and categorize them as 'duplicates' in EcoTaxa.

ecotaxa.tsv table

img_file_name [t]	object_tag [f]
taraeuropa_112_112554211_16.jpg	1
taraeuropa_112_112554211_17.jpg	1
taraeuropa_112_112554211_18.jpg	1
taraeuropa_112_112554211_19.jpg	1
taraeuropa_112_112554211_20.jpg	1
taraeuropa_112_112554211_21.jpg	1
taraeuropa_112_112554211_22.jpg	1
taraeuropa_112_112554211_23.jpg	1
taraeuropa_112_112554211_24.jpg	1
taraeuropa_112_112554211_25.jpg	2
taraeuropa_112_112554211_26.jpg	1
taraeuropa_112_112554211_27.jpg	1
taraeuropa_112_112554211_28.jpg	2
taraeuropa_112_112554211_29.jpg	2
taraeuropa_112_112554211_30.jpg	2
taraeuropa_112_112554211_31.jpg	1
taraeuropa_112_112554211_32.jpg	1
taraeuropa_112_112554211_33.jpg	2
taraeuropa_112_112554211_34.jpg	2
taraeuropa_112_112554211_35.jpg	2
taraeuropa_112_112554211_36.jpg	2
taraeuropa_112_112554211_37.jpg	2
taraeuropa_112_112554211_38.jpg	2
taraeuropa_112_112554211_39.jpg	2
taraeuropa_112_112554211_40.jpg	2
taraeuropa_112_112554211_41.jpg	2
taraeuropa_112_112554211_42.jpg	2
taraeuropa_112_112554211_43.jpg	1
taraeuropa_112_112554211_44.jpg	2
taraeuropa_112_112554211_45.jpg	2

Filters on EcoTaxa

area [pixel] ▾

Category Name

Image Name

Score

Validation date

Prediction date

area [pixel]

circ

depth_max

depth_min

elongation

feret [pixel]

fractal

major [pixel]

mean [0-255]

symetrieh

tag

20.Import images and data into EcoTaxa

Import the work folder of your project into EcoTaxa

For more informations :

<http://piqv.imev-mer.fr> → EcoTaxa tab → ECOTAXA MANUAL

To analyse EcoTaxa tables :

<http://piqv.imev-mer.fr> → EcoTaxa tab → HOW TO PROCESS plankton abundance from FLOWCAM exported data

21.Delete data file

If you need to delete your acquisition you have to :

1. Delete your acquisition in your raw file of your project.

2. Delete your acquisition in the VisualSpreadsheet program.

Launch VisualSpreadsheet program, select File -> Delete Data... The Delete window opens. Select the acquisition you want to delete and click on OK. The Warning window opens, click on OK, your acquisition is deleted.

22. Powering Down the analyzer

- Close all softwares.
- Shutdown the computer via Windows Explorer: the round power button on the top right of the analyzer switches off automatically.

- Turn off the computer screen.
- Switch off the power button behind the FlowCam.

